

Additional File 4. Frequency of CD86⁺ DC-10 cells correlates with T₁₀ cell yield.

Phenotype of one representative preparation (out of eight) of DC-10 is shown (**A**).

Percentages of CD86⁺ DC-10 (CD14⁺CD16⁺) are plotted with yield of the corresponding T₁₀ cells. Line represents linear regression (**B**).